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MODELING THE OPERATION OF AN ASYMMETRIC DISC HARROW FOR SOIL CULTIVATION

Abstract.

A study was conducted on the parameters and operating modes of an asymmetric disk harrow for soil tillage. During the determination of these parameters and modes, the theory of dimensions and similarity of physical quantities was applied. The study revealed patterns that uncover the interrelationships between the parameters, operating modes, environmental properties, and energy indicators of the process. Experimental data from the operation of an asymmetric disk harrow with spherical discs for soil tillage were used as the initial data.

Based on the theory of dimensions, dependencies were obtained to determine the dimensions of the parameters and operating modes of the disk harrow with spherical discs for soil cultivation, as well as soil properties such as draft resistance, depth, working width, speed, soil hardness, and acceleration. Similarity criteria were also determined based on this theory.

Using correlation analysis and the least squares method, the nature of the dependencies and the corresponding coefficients were determined. A graph was constructed to determine the operating modes and parameters of the disk harrow with spherical discs for soil tillage.

To represent the dimensionality of each quantity in the established formulas as a product of power functions of independent quantities (length L , time T , and mass m), we can use the method of dimensional ranks.

Based on the obtained dependencies, it is possible to solve problems related to determining the draft resistance of technical means for soil tillage with disk harrows. Literary sources and well-known scientific studies in the field of soil tillage using a disk harrow as a technical means were used as initial data. Thus, the conducted research established important interrelationships between the parameters and operating modes of the disk harrow for soil tillage using the theory of dimensions and similarity, which can be beneficial for improving agricultural production processes.

Keywords: *dimensional analysis and similarity theory, soil tillage, parameters and modes, hardness, draft resistance, similarity criteria, interrelationship, validation of parameters and modes.*

Introduction

Under conditions of insufficient and unstable moisture, the main objective of soil tillage is to create optimal conditions for maximizing moisture retention and preventing its unproductive loss. Reducing unproductive moisture losses is achieved through a set of measures, including moisture-conserving and soil-protective agricultural methods and technologies [1-3].

When solving practical tasks related to the development of measures to preserve and enhance soil fertility, computational methods play a crucial role. These methods are based on the results of studies of the interaction processes between working tools and soil and the properties determined by these interactions [4-7]. During experimental studies of the interaction processes between working tools and soil, the dynamometry method is often used. However, the use of this method is limited by specific testing conditions. In particular, the comparison of the draft resistance of different technical means needs to be conducted in homogeneous soil conditions, which requires performing numerous experiments in a limited time frame. If homogeneity of soil conditions cannot be achieved, a correction coefficient must be introduced, but its precise determination is impossible [3, 8, 11, 14].

Through modeling in systems analysis, it is possible to determine the relationship between the draft resistance of a technical tool and the physical and mechanical properties of the soil, as well as the parameters and operating modes [9-10, 12-13, 15-18]. Thus, the correction coefficient that accounts for the soil's physical and mechanical properties will already be included in the dependency, allowing for the determination of the draft resistance of the technical tool under different conditions, significantly reducing the scope of experimental research.

Literature Review

The research by the authors [1] identified the horizontal, longitudinal, and vertical components of the working resistance of a compact disc harrow through field experiments. The authors used three values of the attack angle and two values of the tilt angle of the front disc plane, with the third parameter being the working depth measured at the lowest point of the discs. The studied model describes the components of horizontal and vertical resistance as a function of design parameters and disc settings, expressed through the pressure area. It reflects empirical results with 99.7% accuracy

for the horizontal component and 99.9% for the vertical component of resistance.

Researchers [2] aimed to reduce energy consumption during soil tillage by developing a disc working tool that divides the flat cutting surface into separate elements and rotates them at an angle to the plane of rotation. According to the authors, this design allows for soil sliding on the working surface. However, the furrow formation process differs from traditional tillage tools. Mathematical models were presented to determine the parameters of furrows formed by three types of disc tillage tools: those with plain concave and conical ring working surfaces, and those with separate cutting blades mounted obliquely to the plane of rotation.

The authors of the scientific study [3] assessed the performance of three types of tillage discs — standard, notched, and spiral notched — under laboratory conditions with sandy loam soil. For three-dimensional force and torque measurements, researchers employed a transducer and a torque transducer equipped with slip rings.

They determined that employing external power to drive the disc reduced soil forces across all disc types. Various types of cutting edges were examined, significantly influencing the forces on the tillage disc and soil processing.

The researchers [4-5] developed a depth intelligent control system using a pressure sensor to stabilize the depth of the cleaning devices. They constructed regression equations establishing the relationship between various parameters and performance evaluation indices. The optimal parameter combination, determined using software, included a rotation radius of 150 mm and a motion deflection angle of 15.8°. Field tests under these optimal parameters demonstrated that bionic cleaners outperformed conventional flat cleaners, and the depth intelligent control system effectively enhanced the productivity of row cleaners. The researchers assert that straw mulching reached 90.9%, which was 21.3% higher than that of standard cleaners, and the soil surface processing met the agricultural requirements for no-till maize planting.

The study employed a 4×4 factorial design comprising 16 treatment combinations with three replications. Factors included types of disc implements (plain flat disc, wavy disc, notched disc, and helical wavy disc) and travel speed (1.11, 1.67, 2.22, and 2.78 m/s). The authors identified that the type of disc implement significantly influenced all variables.

The study [6-8] was conducted using a disc harrow in a soil bin with paddy field soil covered with straw (100 g/m²) at three speeds and depths to investigate the forces acting on the disc, burial rate of straw of different lengths (7, 13, and 19 cm), soil mobilization area, and changes in bulk density. Results showed that draft, vertical, and lateral forces on the disc increased from 533 to 1236, 243 to 632, and 418 to 1063 N, respectively. The disc tillage tool buried 47 to 86% of the straw in the 0-15 cm layer, with the smallest straw length (7 cm) contributing a maximum of 39%.

In this study [9-10], five vertical tillage tools were evaluated in a winter maize field to compare their effectiveness. All equipment was tested at an operating

speed of 16 km/h and a tillage depth of 100 mm. The study showed that increasing the disc diameter from 457 mm to 559 mm significantly improves residue incorporation, soil opening width, soil disturbance area, and lateral cutting force (by 79%), while reducing residue coverage (by 5%). Increasing the number of flutes from 8 to 13 resulted in a significant reduction in soil sticking (by 39%) and soil opening width (by 29%), but increased residue coverage (by 7%).

The authors of the materials in Article [11-13] address the issue of reducing energy consumption in mountainous agriculture, proposing minimal tillage technology using implements with disk-like working elements such as cultivators and harrows as a solution. They propose a universal working element for minimal tillage, which consists of a spherical disk welded with segmented toothed flat disks. During soil processing with this developed spherical working element, the overlap groove value decreases, ensuring loosening of the ridges formed between the grooves, which improve the technological quality of soil processing and stability of the implement's motion.

The practice of researching technological processes and working tools of technical means for soil tillage indicates the advisability of abandoning the principle of complete structural similarity of the model. It is sufficient to adhere to the analogy of the main indicators of the technological process [14-17].

Currently, there are many different methods, techniques, and approaches that can be conditionally classified as partial analysis [18-20], including the π -theorem method (dimensional analysis), the similarity method, and the method of using fundamental equations.

In the π -theorem (dimensional analysis) method, the necessary data consist of a list of significant physical quantities, including one dependent and a sufficient number of independent ones. This method alone can effectively study dimensions, dimensional homogeneity, and other fundamental concepts used in mathematical modeling of processes [17-22].

Dimensional analysis allows for the determination of similarity criteria without knowing the mathematical relationship between the physical quantities of the process being studied. Any coherent relation describing a physical process can be considered dimensionally homogeneous. Thus, all terms in the equation have the same dimensions, and the parameters involved are merely products of independent dimensions raised to certain powers.

This approach helps to determine how different physical parameters interact with each other and affect the outcomes of soil tillage operations.

The theory of dimensions is based on the idea that physical quantities can be expressed through basic physical units of measurement (e.g., mass, length, time) and dimensionless parameters. This helps simplify tasks and analyze the impact of various factors on the soil tillage process [23-28].

To apply the theory of dimensions and similarity to determine the parameters and operating modes of a disk harrow for soil tillage, it is necessary to:

1. Identify the main physical quantities that influence the soil tillage process, such as the speed of the machine-tractor unit (MTU), resistance force, tillage depth, etc.
2. Express these physical quantities in terms of fundamental units of measurement (mass, length, time).
3. Create dimensionless parameters that reflect the important interrelationships between physical quantities.
4. Use similarity to compare different working conditions, such as different types of working tools, different soil types, different operating modes, etc.

Research Methodology

To improve soil cultivation quality, soil loosening, and ensure the incorporation of stubble, chopped straw, and organic fertilizers into the soil, a universal soil processing implement has been developed at the National Scientific Center "Institute of Agricultural Engineering and Technologies". The versatility of this implement lies in its ability to be used in combination with cultivators, grain drills, and no-till soil processing machines.

The objective of the research is to establish the relationship between the asymmetrical disc harrow, where the kinematic connection between the hitch and the front oscillating beam allows for automatic adjustment of the hitch's distance from the centerline of the harrow, depending on the attack angles of the discs. This problem is addressed by the fact that the asymmetrical disc harrow, as shown in Fig. 1, includes a frame to which the hitch is attached at one end, allowing it to

move along the transverse beam. The frame is mounted on support wheels and is equipped with two oscillating beams—front and rear—arranged in a "V" shape, to which disc batteries are attached, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The hitch is kinematically connected to the front oscillating beam, with the kinematic link being realized through a two-arm lever pivotally mounted to the frame. One arm of the lever is connected to the hitch via a connecting rod, while the other arm, equipped with two end joints, is connected to the front oscillating beam. The two-arm lever features a series of holes for attaching the connecting rod to one of them.

Thanks to this design of the asymmetrical disc harrow, as the attack angles of the discs increase, which leads to a rise in the turning moment exerted on the harrow by the discs, the hitch automatically moves away from the centerline of the harrow due to the kinematic connection between the hitch and the front oscillating beam. Consequently, the moment acting on the harrow from the side of the tractor increases, maintaining the balance of the harrow.

It is also worth noting that if the harrow is intended for use on harder soils, such as black soil, the connecting rod should be attached to a hole farther from the pivot axis of the two-arm lever. This ensures that the hitch moves further away from the centerline of the harrow, maintaining its balance when working on such soils.

An example of this process is shown in Fig. 1 where the asymmetrical disc harrow is illustrated.

Figure 1. General view of an asymmetric disc harrow.

The asymmetrical disc harrow includes a frame mounted on support wheels, which are equipped with a mechanism for shifting the harrow to a transport position. Two oscillating beams, arranged in a "V" shape, are attached to the central beam of the frame using vertical hinges and pairs of washers with holes. The upper washers of each pair are fixed to the central beam of the frame, while the lower washers are attached to the oscillating beams, with each pair of washers connected by tightening bolts.

Each beam is fitted with a row of discs, with the discs in the front and rear rows oriented in opposite directions. This configuration allows for the adjustment of the attack angles of the discs by rotating the beams around the hinges, with the beams being moved out of the holes. The hitch is attached to one end of the transverse beam of the frame and can move along this beam, equipped with a lock to secure it in a set position, and is kinematically connected to the front oscillating beam. This kinematic connection can be implemented

hydraulically, using two hydraulic cylinders connected by oil lines, or mechanically.

The mechanical connection is realized with a two-arm lever pivotally mounted to the frame. One arm of the lever is connected to the hitch via a connecting rod, while the other arm, equipped with two end joints, is attached to the front oscillating beam. If the harrow is designed for use on uniform soils, such as only black soils, then the two-arm lever has only one hole for attaching the connecting rod. However, if the harrow is designed for use on three types of soils—gray, black, and clayey—then three holes are provided.

Before starting work with the harrow, depending on the soil type, the connecting rod is attached to the appropriate hole in the lever. For instance, if the harrow is to be used on the heaviest clay soils, the connecting rod is attached to the hole at the end of the lever arm. In this case, the initial distance K from the hitch to the centerline of the harrow will be maximized. Consequently, the turning moment transmitted from the tractor's pulling force to the harrow will be maximized, balancing the increased turning moment exerted on the harrow due to the resistance of the clay soil. Conversely, if the harrow is to be used on light sandy soils, the connecting rod is attached to the hole farthest from the end of the lever arm. Here, the initial distance K from the hitch to the centerline of the harrow will be minimized, but the turning moment from the tractor's pulling force will be sufficient to balance the lesser moment resulting from the lower resistance of the sandy soil.

Following this, depending on the required depth of soil processing, the necessary attack angles of the discs are set. The harrow is then shifted to the transport position using a corresponding wheel mechanism, the tightening bolts are removed from the washer pairs, and the lock is released. The tractor operator adjusts the oscillating beams to the required angles, inserts the tightening bolts into the new matching holes, and secures the washers with bolts. When the front beam is rotated, the movement is transmitted through the kinematic link (connecting rod, two-arm lever, and connecting rod) to the hitch, which automatically moves along the beam to the required distance. Increasing the attack angles of the discs increases the distance K , which in turn in-

creases the turning moment transmitted from the tractor's pulling force to the harrow, balancing the increased turning moment due to the deeper soil processing. Conversely, decreasing the attack angles reduces the distance K , maintaining equilibrium of the two moments.

Thus, during operation of this asymmetrical disc harrow on various soils and at different attack angles, the balance of turning moments is maintained. Since these moments act in opposite directions, the total turning moment acting on the harrow will be zero, meaning that the harrow remains balanced and operates as if it were symmetrical. At the same time, it is significantly simpler than a symmetrical harrow, has a lower specific metal content, and provides better soil processing quality.

After the disc harrow has passed over the field, the upper layer of the soil is leveled and has a fine-grained structure, with the maximum size of soil clods not exceeding the minimum clod size allowed by agronomic requirements for pre-sowing treatment. The presence of a loose and fine-grained structure in the upper soil layer prevents moisture loss and the formation of cracks on the field surface.

The inclination angle of the working elements relative to the vertical is adjusted using holes spaced at a 5-degree interval, while the inclination angle relative to the direction of movement is adjusted by rotating their supports on the brackets and securing them in a specific position.

Multifactor experiments were conducted on the experimental fields of the National Scientific Center 'Institute of Mechanization and Electrification of Agriculture.' The following parameters were used as evaluation criteria: soil loosening degree D , the height of surface h_p and bottom h_d irregularities of the tilled soil layer, and the traction resistance R of the working tool per unit of working width.

The proposed method for researching the efficiency of an asymmetric disc harrow equipped with a device for stabilizing its movement from lateral displacement relative to the direction of the unit's motion is presented. The general view of the asymmetric disc harrow with a stabilization device for lateral movement is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. General view of the asymmetric disc harrow with a stabilization device for lateral movement.

Thus, the method involves the following operations: a 100-meter-long and approximately 10-meter-wide section of the selected field is chosen. A machine-tractor unit with an asymmetric disc harrow without the stabilization device makes three passes over the 100-meter section. The tractor follows a marked path during the first pass. After the first pass, the deviation of the unit in the direction perpendicular to the tractor's movement is measured. The frequency of measurements should be such that at least three measurements are taken for the smallest wave of oscillation. The measurements are recorded in a log. After the measurements, the second and third adjacent passes of the machine-tractor unit are conducted, with the condition of minimal overlap of the processed field width by the asymmetric disc harrow.

After three passes, the width of the continuously processed field by the machine-tractor unit with the asymmetric disc harrow is measured every meter, and the average width of the processed strip by the machine-tractor unit for the three passes is determined. The ratio of this average value to the theoretical total width will be the coefficient of utilization of the working width by the asymmetric disc harrow.

After completing this part of the study, similar actions are carried out with the asymmetric disc harrow equipped with a device for stabilizing lateral movement relative to the tractor's movement. The result of the study is a comparison of the working width utilization coefficients of the asymmetric disc harrow.

Our preliminary research has shown that the installation of the stabilization device on the asymmetric disc harrow (Fig. 2) increases the productivity of the machine-tractor unit with the asymmetric disc harrow by 15-20% due to the reduction of overlap during adjacent passes. At the same time, the quality of disking is improved, and the control of the machine-tractor unit is simplified.

To implement the experimental plan, it was necessary to select a sufficiently large plot, ensuring the homogeneity of the soil's physical and mechanical properties across its area. Calculations showed that the minimum required plot size is 200 x 24 m. The planned length for conducting one experiment is 50 m. During implementation, the electrical signal from the sensor is amplified and recorded on tape as an oscillogram. The length of implementation should ensure at least 100 measurements (preferably 250-300) of the ordinate lengths of the oscillograph beam's deviation from the zero line. To adequately reflect the oscillogram in digital form, it is necessary to have at least three measurements of the ordinate deviations on the smallest har-

monic of the oscillogram, which reflects the fluctuations in the traction resistance of the asymmetric disc harrow.

Results.

Spherical discs are widely used as working elements in disc plows, cultivators, and harrows. However, their impact on the soil remains insufficiently studied to this day due to the limited amount of research conducted in this area [1-5].

During operation, soil particles rise along the working surface of the disc, move across it, and are then thrown to the side. Let's consider the movement of soil particles along the working surface of the disc [6-10]. To do this, we replace the spherical disc with a conical disc with the same angle θ at the vertex.

The soil particles on the disc's surface perform a complex motion: a translational rotational movement with the disc and a relative movement along the disc. As a result, particles that land on the surface of the disc will begin to move along a certain trajectory l_A in relation to absolute motion and along a trajectory l_B in relation to the disc's relative motion, as shown in (Fig. 3). The absolute velocity of soil particle movement on the disc's surface represents the geometric sum of the translational velocity V_p and the relative velocity V_B [11-15].

At any given moment, the position of the soil particles on the surface of the disc is determined by two generalized coordinates: the angular displacement of the particle in absolute motion α and the radius vector R_R . These parameters are used to describe the position of the particles.

A soil particle located at a certain point O_1 on the disc's surface is subjected to the following forces (Fig. 3):

The designations of the forces acting on the soil particle are as follows:

- $G = m \cdot g$ - The force of gravity;
- $F_B = m \cdot \dot{\alpha}^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta$ - Centrifugal inertia force caused by the translational rotational motion with angular velocity ω ;
- $F_{k1} = 2 \cdot m \cdot \dot{\alpha} \cdot \dot{R}_R \cdot \sin \theta$ - The Coriolis force, which arises due to the rotational motion of the disc with angular velocity ω and the relative movement along the radius vector;
- $F_{k2} = 2 \cdot m \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot R_R \cdot \omega$ - The Coriolis force from the component $(\dot{\beta} \cdot R_R)$ for the relative velocity;
- $F_T = f \cdot N_d$ - The friction force;
- $N_d = m \cdot g \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \cos \theta + F_B \cdot \cos \theta - F_{k2} \cdot \cos \theta$ - The normal reaction of the disc;

Or, in general, it can be expressed in the following interrelationship:

$$N_d = m \cdot g \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \cos \theta + m \cdot \dot{\alpha}^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - 2 \cdot m \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot R_R \cdot \omega \cdot \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

In these equations:

β - the angular displacement of the particle in relative motion;

f - the coefficient of friction of the soil on the disc.

Figure 3. Diagram of forces acting on the soil particle.

Using the well-known D'Alembert principle, we will formulate the equation for the relative motion of the soil particle on the surface of the disc:

$$m \cdot \ddot{R}_R = m \cdot g \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \cos \theta + m \cdot R_R \cdot \dot{\alpha}^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - 2 \cdot m \cdot R_R \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot \omega \cdot \cos \theta - f \cdot N_d \cdot \cos \varphi \quad (2)$$

$$m \cdot \ddot{\beta} = m \cdot g \cdot \sin \alpha - 2 \cdot m \cdot \dot{\alpha} \cdot \dot{R}_R \cdot \sin \theta - f \cdot N_d \cdot \sin \varphi \quad (3)$$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{\dot{R}_R}{\sqrt{(R_R)^2 + (R_R \cdot \dot{\beta})^2}}; \sin \varphi = \frac{R_R \cdot \dot{\beta}}{\sqrt{(R_R)^2 + (R_R \cdot \dot{\beta})^2}} \quad (4)$$

Considering that $\alpha = \delta - \beta$ (where $\delta = \omega \cdot t$ - the angular displacement of the disc), we obtain the following relationships:

$$\dot{\alpha} = \omega - \dot{\beta}, \ddot{\alpha} = -\ddot{\beta}, \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{R}_R = & g \cdot \cos[\delta - \beta] \cdot \cos \theta + R_R \cdot [\omega - \dot{\beta}]^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - \\ & - 2 \cdot R_R \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot \omega \cdot \cos \theta - \\ & - f \cdot \left[\begin{array}{l} g \cdot \cos[\delta - \beta] \cdot \cos \theta + \\ + [\omega - \dot{\beta}]^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - \\ - 2 \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot R_R \cdot \omega \cdot \cos \theta \end{array} \right] \cdot \frac{\dot{R}_R}{\sqrt{(R_R)^2 + (R_R \cdot \dot{\beta})^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_R \cdot \ddot{\beta} = & g \cdot \sin[\delta - \beta] - 2 \cdot [\omega - \dot{\beta}] \cdot \dot{R}_R \cdot \sin \theta - \\ & - f \cdot \left[\begin{array}{l} g \cdot \cos[\delta - \beta] \cdot \cos \theta + \\ + [\omega - \dot{\beta}]^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - \\ - 2 \cdot \dot{\beta} \cdot R_R \cdot \omega \cdot \cos \theta \end{array} \right] \cdot \frac{R_R \cdot \dot{\beta}}{\sqrt{(R_R)^2 + (R_R \cdot \dot{\beta})^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equations (6) and (7) represent a general system of complex differential equations that describe the motion of particles over the uneven surface of the spherical disc. This system contains nonlinear inhomogeneous second-order equations and does not have an analytical solution in conventional functions. To find the solution to this system, numerical methods can be employed; for example, we can use the Runge-Kutta method [4].

Based on the obtained equality (5) and taking into account expression (1), the differential equations for the relative motion of the particle will be as follows:

The disc rotates due to its rolling motion over the soil surface. Therefore, soil particles located on its surface hardly move along the arc of the circular trajectory of the disc, as their motion is primarily restricted to the radial direction. Thus, we can assume that soil particles move radially relative to the disc, meaning $\alpha = \delta$ and $\dot{\alpha} = \omega$, and the equations for their relative motion will then take the following form:

$$\ddot{R}_R = g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta + R_R \cdot [\omega]^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - f \cdot [g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta + [\omega]^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta] \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{R}_R - R_R \cdot [\omega]^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta + f \cdot [\omega]^2 \cdot R_R \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta = \\ = g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta - f \cdot [g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{R}_R - R_R \cdot ([\omega]^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta - f \cdot [\omega]^2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta) = \\ = g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta - f \cdot [g \cdot \cos[\omega \cdot t] \cdot \cos \theta] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Solving this equation and considering that:

$$f = \frac{\sin \theta_t}{\cos \theta_t} = \tan \theta_t \quad (11)$$

$$\omega = \frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \quad (12)$$

where θ_t is the angular coefficient of friction of the soil on the spherical disc;

V_p is the translational velocity of the spherical disc;

R is the radius of the spherical disc.

We obtain the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} R_R = 0,5 \cdot \left[R_{R0} + \frac{R^2 \cdot g \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t]}{[V_p \cdot \cos \delta]^2 \cdot [\cos[\theta_t] - \sin[\theta - \theta_t]]} \right] \times \\ \times \left[e^{\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \sqrt{\frac{\sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot t}{\cos[\theta_t]}}} + e^{-\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \sqrt{\frac{\sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot t}{\cos[\theta_t]}}} \right] - \\ - \frac{R^2 \cdot g \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot \cos\left[\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \cdot t\right]}{[V_p \cdot \cos \delta]^2 \cdot [\cos[\theta_t] + \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t]]} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using equation (13), we can determine the relative velocity of soil particles moving along the surface of the spherical disc, as well as calculate the moment, the

angle of displacement, and the speed at which they slide off the surface of the disc. The relative velocity is computed using the established equation:

$$\begin{aligned} V_B = \dot{R}_R = \frac{0,5 \cdot V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \times \left[R_{R0} + \frac{R^2 \cdot g \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t]}{[V_p \cdot \cos \delta]^2 \cdot [\cos[\theta_t] - \sin[\theta - \theta_t]]} \right] \times \\ \times \left[e^{\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \sqrt{\frac{\sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot t}{\cos[\theta_t]}}} - e^{-\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \sqrt{\frac{\sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot t}{\cos[\theta_t]}}} \right] + \\ + \frac{R \cdot g \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t] \cdot \sin\left[\frac{V_p \cdot \cos \delta}{R} \cdot t\right]}{[V_p \cdot \cos \delta] \cdot [\cos[\theta_t] + \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta - \theta_t]]} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Equations (13) and (14) establish the relationship between all the factors that determine the movement of particles on the surface of the working spherical disc.

Analyzing (13) and (14), it has been established that under certain conditions, the motion and speed of soil particle displacement in relative motion primarily depend on the speed of the agricultural machine and the angle of attack of the spherical disc.

Using the derived relationships (13) and (14), graphical dependencies were constructed (Fig. 4) that illustrate the changes in relative motion and relative velocity of soil particles at different values of δ and parameters such as $\theta = 60^\circ$; translational velocity $V_p = 1,5$ m/s.

Figure 4. Character of the change in relative motion of the soil particle on the spherical disc at different values of the angle δ .

From the analysis of the graphs, it is evident that as the angle of attack of the spherical disc increases, the movement of soil particles on the disc becomes slower.

Using equation (13) and after establishing a limited value for the radius vector $R_R = \frac{R}{\sin \theta}$, we can determine the time during which the particle remains on the spherical disc. During this time, the disc rotates by an angle $\delta_1 = \omega \cdot t_1$. By substituting t_1 into equation (14), we can find the relative velocity of the particle at the moment it is ejected from the spherical disc.

Thus, the developed mathematical models that describe the motion of soil particles on the working surface of the spherical disc have shown that the intensity of its impact on the soil depends on the angle of attack of the disc, its diameter, and the speed of the agricultural machine.

Discussion.

The results of the study demonstrate the importance of a comprehensive approach to determining the draft resistance of soil tillage implements. The application of dimensional analysis theory has simplified the process of modeling and analyzing the interaction between a disk harrow and the soil, significantly easing the determination of optimal operating parameters.

In particular, it was established that the energy dimensionless complex is highly sensitive to changes in the geometric parameters of the implement and the physical properties of the soil, such as its hardness. This indicates that effective adjustment of the working tools of the disk harrow can significantly reduce the energy consumption required for soil tillage.

Additionally, an interesting conclusion was drawn regarding the stronger dependence on the geometry of the working tool rather than the dynamic characteristics of the process (such as the unit's speed). This suggests

that in practice, adjusting the geometric parameters of the implement will have a greater impact on reducing draft resistance than altering the operating modes.

Further research could focus on developing methods for adaptive adjustment of implement parameters based on specific soil conditions. This would enhance the efficiency of their use and reduce energy costs in agricultural operations.

Thus, the study's results confirm the significance of the approaches considered for optimizing the operation of agricultural machinery and reducing soil tillage costs, which is a crucial task for the modern agro-industrial complex.

Conclusions.

The application of dimensional analysis and similarity theory helps to simplify the analysis and determination of parameters for soil tillage implements and their working tools, making their comparison more objective. This approach can be beneficial for optimizing the performance of agricultural machinery and improving the efficiency of soil tillage in agricultural production.

In the development of soil tillage implements, computational methods based on the results of studies on the interaction of their working tools with the soil and its properties play an essential role.

Modeling in systems analysis allows for determining the relationship between machine draft resistance and the soil's physical and mechanical properties, as well as operating parameters and modes.

Using the obtained graphical dependency, one can determine the draft resistance of a disk harrow with spherical discs by specifying soil properties, parameters, and operating modes, thereby significantly reducing the scope of experimental research.

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